

Designing a Video Script of Travelin Application at PT Angkasa Pura II Palembang

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to design a video script for the *Travelin* application at PT. Angkasa Pura II Palembang to facilitate customers' digital check-in and assist support officers. Employing a Research and Development (R&D) approach adapted from Plomp (1997) and utilising a qualitative descriptive design, the script design process included five stages: (1) preliminary investigation, (2) design, (3) realisation/development, (4) testing, evaluation, and revision, and (5) implementation. Data collection techniques comprised literature reviews and interviews, with thematic analysis applied to the interview data. Three experts, selected purposely—a scriptwriting expert, an Indonesian language expert, and an English language expert—participated in the script revision. Key findings from experts' feedback highlighted the need to simplify sentences, enhance content engagement, incorporate contemporary language, and avoid redundancy. Language-specific suggestions included refining diction, addressing Indonesian affixes (e.g., *di-*), italicising English terms, and converting complex sentences to simpler structures. This refined script is anticipated to enhance the effectiveness of the *Travelin* application video at PT. Angkasa Pura II Palembang offers clear guidance to customers and improves digital security check-in processes. The novelty of the study focuses on providing insights into creating effective instructional videos for technology-based services within a particular organizational context.

Keywords: *Design, Informational Video, Travelin Application, Video Script*

Over the past few decades, technological advancements have continuously shaped and transformed the aviation industry to drive constant innovation. It is crucial because the development of the aviation industry is impacted significantly. The development influenced variables such as sustained economic growth, economical air travel, and rising international linkages due to a significant increase in air passengers (Yanwardhana, 2022). These trends pose new challenges for airport management, air traffic control, and the provision of quality services to passengers. PT. Angkasa Pura II as the only one Indonesia's top airport operator, plays a crucial role in ensuring efficient airport infrastructure and user-friendly services to meet the needs of passengers. By maintaining high safety standards and providing seamless travel experiences, PT. Angkasa Pura II has emerged as a leader in Indonesia's aviation industry.

To meet these evolving demands, PT. Angkasa Pura II has embraced mobile technology, particularly through its new application, *Travelin*, which improves passenger convenience and efficiency. This application demonstrates how mobile applications have revolutionised travel by

providing easy access to essential information and services. In the aviation sector, this application has become an invaluable tool for passengers. With features such as real-time flight updates, ticket booking, online check-in, and airport navigation, the application not only simplifies travel but also enhances the overall passenger experience (Syukur, 2023). By embracing the latest technology, PT. Angkasa Pura II is establishing itself as a leader in digital innovation in aviation.

To introduce the Travelin application to wider customers and passengers, PT Angkasa Pura II Palembang needed to socialise the application through a video. The video was chosen by the media because it was identified as the most effective tool in socialisation due to its ability to combine visual and audio elements in conveying messages that affected the audience's emotions and cognition more effectively than other media (Liu & Huang, 2016). However, to produce a good video, it needs a powerful script as the soul. A video script serves as a guide for a script writer in transforming ideas into videos, pictures, or images (Tristiawati, 2014). Hence, it was needed to design an informative and inspiring video script to explain the key features and benefits of the Travelin application in an engaging and easy-to-understand manner.

Learning from some previous studies related to designing video script for promotion conducted by Andini (2024), Fadlurrahman (2023), Viranda, (2024), and Yandi, Shahab, Sari, (2023), all share a common objective: to develop effective video scripts for promoting tourism destinations. These previous studies consistently employ variations of the Research and Development (R&D) methodology as their research framework, emphasizing a systematic and iterative approach to script development. Furthermore, all studies rely on a combination of literature reviews, observations, and interviews to gather relevant data. Each study also involves the critical evaluation of the developed scripts by a panel of experts, such as language specialists, scriptwriting professionals, and video editing experts, ensuring the quality and effectiveness of the final product.

Despite their shared focus and methodological similarities, the studies conducted by Andini (2024), Fadlurrahman (2023), Viranda (2024), and Yandi et al (2023) also exhibit distinct characteristics. Each study focuses on a unique tourism destination, ranging from a beach of New Octarina in Batam (Viranda, 2024) to reastaurants of Pempek Cek Yati (Andini, 2024) and Dapoer Cinta in Palembang (Fadlurrahman, 2023), and a park Green Canyon in Lahat (Yandi et al., 2023). The specific adaptations of the R&D method vary across the studies, Viranda (2024) and Fadlurrahman (2023) utilized Plomp's model while Andini (2024), Yandi et al (2023.) adopted modifications proposed by Sukmadinata's model. Moreover, the data analysis techniques employed by the researchers differ, with some opting for qualitative descriptive analysis (Fadlurrahman, 2023) and others employing coding analysis (Andini, 2024). Consequently, the findings and recommendations for script improvement are unique to each study, reflecting the specific context and challenges associated with promoting each tourism destination.

Redarding the purpose of this study, it intended to know the steps in designing proper video script in Bahasa Indonesia and English versions for the Travelin application using a Research and Development Method adapted from Plomp's theory (1997). The Bahasa Indonesia version was intended for the narration of the video for Indonesian viewers and the English version was for subtitles for the video for foreign viewers.

METHOD

This study used the Research and Development (R&D) Method, which was developed from Plomp's (1997), with a Descriptive Qualitative research design. Creswell (2014) describes qualitative research as an enquiry process that investigates social or human problems utilising a variety of methodological approaches. Plomp's model was chosen because it was allowed to maintain each step in the context of the research and its completion (Gustiani, 2019). By following

this model, development research produced products that were highly relevant, effective, and valid for use (Plomp, 1997). In this study, the Travelin application's video script was transformed into a reliable and efficient information source for video viewers by the application of Plomp's Model in descriptive composition. It comprises five stages: preliminary investigation, design, realisation/construction, testing, evaluation, revision, and implementation, guided by the development process as displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Plomp's Research and Development Method (Plomp, 1997)

Participants of the Study

The participants of this study contributed to the data of the study to improve the video script quality which conducted by R & D Method by Plomp's Model (1987) with qualitative design. Three participants were chosen purposely using a purposive sampling method due to their respective fields (Creswell, 2014). They were a scriptwriting expert, a Bahasa Indonesia expert, and an English expert who were responsible for their expertise. The expert of scriptwriting ensured the content of the video script was clear, compelling, and coherent, creating a narrative flow that highlighted the application's unique features and benefits. The Bahasa Indonesia expert localised the script to suit the Indonesian audience, using appropriate Indonesian language to build trust and connection with the local viewers. Finally, the English expert makes grammatical accuracy, enhancing the script's clarity and credibility based on English rules for foreign viewers.

Data Collecting Techniques

There were two techniques for collecting the data, namely literature study and interview. The literature study was done to develop a script for the Travelin Application by searching extensively for relevant theoretical sources to guide the scriptwriting process, examining books, academic journals, and research articles from both printed and online sources. Additionally, the data for the script improvement were collected using semi-structured interviews with the experts. Magaldi and Berler (2020) defined semi-structured interviews as exploratory in character and in-depth discovery. Each interview was in 45 minutes one-on-one as a direct method of obtaining information from an expert at the expert's preference place. All the interviews were recorded by a voice recorder.

The interview questions for the scriptwriting expert were about structuring information effectively and narrative structure based on the theory of Satoeasa's (2020). The questions about standard language usage and clarity in Bahasa Indonesia based on EYD 5th edition (2022) were then posed to the Bahasa Indonesia expert. The English expert had been interviewed about language usage and writing clarity in English according to Herring's (2016) theory. To verify each interview results, member checking was applied so that the participants could give validation and determine reliability of the interview results. Participants receive their data or results back to make sure they are accurate and in line with their experiences (Birt et al., 2016).

Data Analysing Techniques

In literature studies, specific research questions and objectives related to the Travelin Application were identified after analysing references from the printed and online sources. Then, the relevance and credibility of the studies were evaluated to uncover key insights.. The collected data were ultimately used to design a script showcasing the application's features and benefits.

Furthermore, the interview data were processed using thematic analysis by Patton (2015) in which the analysis emphasised on identifying, analysing, and interpreting the collected interviews data. Firstly, listening to recordings, taking note of the important information from the voice recordings of interviews. Secondly, identifying the important information into categories such as issues identified and recommendations for improvement, to facilitate focus on revision. After that, comparing and aligning the feedback from the three experts to find the themes, commonalities, and differences, and ensure all revisions have been thoroughly implemented. Finally, once all revisions have been made, evaluate the final script to ensure all feedback has been properly implemented and request final feedback from experts if needed to ensure the quality of the script.

FINDINGS

The findings in this research were defined into three abstractions. They were Preliminary Investigation, Model Development, and Implementation based on the theory of Research and Development Method by Plomp (1997).

1. Preliminary Investigation

There were two stages in the preliminary study, namely literature study and product arrangement.

1.1 Literature Study

During the literature study, a research framework was created by relying on various sources to collect relevant data and information. In this case, the information was searched through the internet from official websites and other printed sources related to the Travelin application. The source of information was used to obtain information about the Travelin application including the official website of PT Angkasa Pura as the main source of information

for this application. The information was about the purpose of developing the application, key features, and usage guides in this website. From the user reviews, various review platforms such as Google Play Store or App Store provide reviews and ratings from users who have used the Travelin app. The reviews were used to gain insight into the actual user experience, advantages, disadvantages, and problems which arose during use. Moreover, news, articles or blogs about the Travelin app were used to provide in-depth reviews of new features, updates or recent developments related to this app. In addition the information of the Travelin application was also downloaded to learn about its features. This step was important as it allowed the viewers to gain a practical understanding of the app's functionality, users' interface and users' experience first-hand.

1.2 Product Arrangement

After gathering information about the material and learning about the script in the previous stage, pre-designing combining the information was done by beginning to outline the script's composition. Satoeasa (2020) suggests the following outline of the information generated in the script:

1. Hook, it grabbed the audience's attention within the first few seconds.
2. Prologue, it gave a brief background about Travelin and explained why this video was important.
3. Body, it conveyed key information and details about Travelin.
4. Conclusion, it summarised the key points and reinforced the main message.
5. Closing, it provided a call to action and closed the video on a high note.

1.3 Model Development

This step included design, implementation, and testing (including evaluation, and revision) to make a proper video script about Travelin Application.

2. Designing

The data from the preliminary investigation about the content and script framework were used in designing the script. In addition, the ideas of the script were developed from the previously established structure by creating script elements such as the hook, prologue, body, conclusion, and closing, as outlined by Satoeasa (2020). As a hook, the script began with an attention-grabbing line to give a brief introduction about the app and to catch viewers' curiosity. Then the prologue provided a quick explanation of the app's background and usage. The body of the script explained detailed information about the Travelin Application such as history, features, functions, and benefits in using it. The goal was to provide viewers with an understanding of what the Travelin Application can achieve. After focusing on all of the details, the script concluded by summarising the important themes to provide viewers with an idea of what the app has accomplished so far and what the future may hold. Finally, the script ended on a favourable note, encouraging viewers to try out the Travelin Application for themselves.

3. Realisation/Construction

At this point, the design was developed into a trial or first version script through descriptive paragraphs in Bahasa Indonesia version. These paragraphs detailed the information obtained from preliminary study regarding the Travelin Application using Microsoft Word program.

4. Testing, Evaluation, Revision

At this point, the first script draft was submitted to the three experts for testing the properness in its writing, Bahasa Indonesia, and English. From the interviews, the experts provided feedback on the first draft as the evaluation in the forms of notes, comments, and ideas. The script, then, was revised based on the interview data, taking into account all of the suggestions. The following were changes based on experts' evaluation:

4.1 Scriptwriting Expert

The scriptwriting expert was responsible to check the suitability with the elements of video script writing according to the theory of Satoeasa (2020). It provided 8 comments and suggestions, emphasised on the use of updated and trendy sentences to attract the audience's attention.

1. Hook: the sentence was informative but not interesting enough. It was suggested that the hook could start with a fact, anecdote, quote, or experience story.
2. Prologue: it was suggested to improve the sentence prefix to transfer the information smoother. It was also suggested to improve the beginning of the sentence to clarify the purpose of the Travelin application.
3. Body: there were repetition paragraphs about the history of the Travelin application and its features both in prologue and body; better to keep it in the prologue. The sentence prefix had to be simpler.
4. Conclusion: there was no section encouraging viewers to download or visit the website for more information and there were also a few irrelevant sentences omitted.

4.2 Bahasa Indonesia Expert

After finishing the revision based on the comments from the script writing expert, the script was then given to the Bahasa Indonesia expert for improving in Bahasa Indonesia. Based on the interview, this expert's comments as follows:

1. The use of English words in Indonesian text had to be italicised (example: Bye-bye into *Bye-bye*, happy into *happy*).
2. The use of informal words such as (*Ga cuma itu, bikin, dapetin*) were italicised.
3. In the prologue, the part '*di design*' should be changed to '*didesain*', the prefix *di-* should be integrated to the verbs.

4. In the last paragraph of the body, the word '*di tempat*' is changed to '*ditempat*', the prefix *di-* should be separated to the places.
5. To make the script smoother, the use of words should be corrected such as:
 - '*Dengan resminya peluncuran*' is simplified to '*Peluncuran resmi*'.
 - '*Sebagai pengantar baru*' is changed to a better word which is '*Sebagai pionir baru*'.
 - '*simbol persatuan*' is replaced to be '*simbol perpaduan*'.

4.3 English Expert.

After revising the Bahasa Indonesia version, the script was then translated into English and submitted to the English expert for evaluation. The English expert gave two comments as follows:

1. The choice of diction: example in the body section, the words "*Sure security*" should be replaced with "*Guarantee security*"
2. The grammar revision for clauses forms: example in conclusion section, the words "*From booking tickets*" are better replaced by clauses, "*from purchasing tickets*" to make the script more appropriate.

5. Implementation

In this stage, all the comments and suggestions for the script improvement from the three experts were implemented into the trial script. It was revised as the final product as the script for Travelin Application video. The Bahasa Indonesia version and English version are displayed in Table 1.

Table 1 The Final Version of Travelin Appilcation Video Script

Bahas Indonesia Version	English Version
HOOK	
<p><i>Bye-bye</i> drama bandara! Dengan Travelin, kamu bisa nikmatin perjalanan tanpa stress dan langsung santai <i>kayak</i> di pantai karena tinggal tap langsung <i>happy</i>.</p>	<p>Bye-bye airport drama! With Travelin, you can enjoy stress-free travelling and instantly relax like at the beach because all you have to do is just tap and be happy.</p>
PROLOGUE	
<p>Dulu namanya INAirport, sekarang jadi Travelin, aplikasi keren dari PT Angkasa Pura II buat penumpang bandara. Ada fitur baru, seperti Airport ID dan teknologi pengenalan wajah. Makin canggih, makin asik, dan sudah ribuan pengguna yang <i>download</i>.</p> <p>Aplikasi Travelin dibuat oleh PT Angkasa Pura II untuk memberikan pengalaman terbaik bagi masyarakat dalam melakukan perjalanan udara. Dengan fitur-fitur inovatif seperti <i>E-check in</i>, <i>Transportation</i>, <i>Shop & Dine</i>, dan lain-lain, aplikasi ini memungkinkan pengguna untuk mendapatkan informasi dan layanan yang lebih nyaman dan mudah dalam bepergian melalui bandara-bandara PT Angkasa Pura II.</p> <p>Berbagai tujuan didesain demi kenyamanan selama perjalanan, antara lain untuk memudahkan pengguna dalam mendapatkan informasi terkait penerbangan dan bandara. Dengan pemberitahuan <i>real-time</i> tentang status penerbangan, lokasi toko, dan fasilitas bandara, setiap langkah menjadi lebih mudah. Nikmati perjalanan yang lancar dan efisien karena Travelin hadir untuk memastikan kenyamanan dan keefektifan selama liburanmu. Keunggulan utamanya? Integrasi yang <i>seamless</i> antara seluruh <i>stakeholders</i>, menjadikan setiap momenmu tak terlupakan.</p> <p>Terdapat beberapa fitur yang memberikan kenyamanan saat bepergian seperti <i>Business Opportunity</i> yang menyediakan informasi mengenai komersial dan peluang usaha di bandara; fitur <i>Emergency</i> yang memungkinkan pengguna untuk langsung terhubung dengan personel di bandara saat membutuhkan bantuan.</p>	<p>It used to be called INAirport, now it's Travelin, a cool app from PT Angkasa Pura II for airport passengers. There are new features, such as Airport ID and facial recognition technology. More advanced, more fun, and thousands of users have downloaded it.</p> <p>The Travelin app was created by PT Angkasa Pura II to provide the best experience for people travelling by air. With innovative features such as E-check in, Transportation, Shop & Dine, and others, this application allows users to get information and services that are more convenient and easier in travelling through PT Angkasa Pura II airports.</p> <p>Various purposes are designed for the convenience of travelling, including making it easier for users to get information related to flights and airports. With real-time notifications on flight status, store locations, and airport facilities, every step becomes easier. Enjoy a smooth and efficient journey as Travelin is here to ensure comfort and effectiveness during your holiday. The main advantage? Seamless integration between all stakeholders, making every moment unforgettable.</p> <p>There are several features that provide convenience while travelling such as Business Opportunity that provides information on commercial and business opportunities at the airport; Emergency feature that allows users to directly connect with personnel at the airport when they need assistance.</p>

<p>Aplikasi Travelin bertujuan untuk meningkatkan kenyamanan dan efisiensi dalam penerbangan dan berwisata, serta untuk mendukung ekosistem transportasi dan pariwisata.</p>	<p>The Travelin app aims to improve convenience and efficiency in flying and travelling, as well as to support the transport and tourism ecosystem.</p>
BODY	
<p>Aplikasi Travelin dirancang utk memudahkan pengguna dalam melakukan perjalanan udara. Pada fitur sebelum keberangkatan atau <i>before you fly</i>, pengguna dapat melakukan <i>e-check in</i>, menemukan informasi tentang transportasi publik di bandara, toko-toko dan restoran, serta melakukan transaksi online di bandara. Selain itu, pengguna juga dapat menemukan informasi tentang layanan premium di bandara, membaca buku elektronik, dan mengaktifkan SIM elektronik.</p> <p>Kemudian, ada fitur keren yaitu fitur saat di bandara atau <i>while you're here</i> di Travelin. Di sini kamu bisa <i>dapetin</i> info tentang destinasi wisata sekitar bandara, akses Wi-Fi, dan berita terkini. Plus, bisa langsung <i>nyambung</i> ke personel bandara kalo butuh bantuan, transaksi online pakai LinkAja, dan mencari tahu hiburan apa saja yang lagi <i>hot</i> di bandara. <i>Gak cuma</i> itu, kamu juga bisa <i>temuin</i> info tentang hotel di sekitar bandara dan layanan premium di bandara.</p> <p>Jangan lupa fitur penting lainnya, Airport ID, yang bakal <i>bikin</i> perjalananmu makin lancar dengan teknologi canggih TravelinPass.</p> <p>TravelinPass adalah fitur yang memungkinkan pengguna untuk melakukan verifikasi wajah dan memproses keberangkatan penerbangan dengan teknologi pengenalan wajah (<i>biometric face recognition</i>). TravelinPass memungkinkan kamu untuk langsung menuju <i>autogate</i> di <i>Security Check Point</i> (SCP), tanpa harus mampir ke konter <i>check-in</i>. Kamu bahkan bisa mendapatkan informasi tentang peluang bisnis di bandara dan update penerbangan <i>real-time</i> langsung dari <i>Flight Information Display System</i> (FIDS).</p> <p>Aplikasi ini juga memungkinkan pengguna untuk menemukan informasi yang</p>	<p>The Travelin app is designed to make air travel easier for users. In the “before you fly” feature, users can e-check in, find information about public transport at the airport, shops and restaurants, and conduct online transactions at the airport. In addition, users can also find information about premium services at the airport, read electronic books, and activate SIM electronics.</p> <p>Then, there's the awesome “while you're here” feature on Travelin. Here you can find information about tourist destinations around the airport, Wi-Fi access, and the latest news. Plus, you can directly connect to airport personnel if you need help, make online transactions using LinkAja, and find out what entertainment is hot at the airport. Not only that, you can also find information about hotels around the airport and premium services at the airport.</p> <p>Don't forget another important feature, Airport ID, which will make your journey smoother with TravelinPass' advanced technology.</p> <p>TravelinPass is a feature that allows users to perform facial verification and process flight departures with biometric face recognition technology. TravelinPass allows you to go straight to the autogate at the Security Check Point (SCP), without having to stop by the check-in counter. You can even get information about business opportunities at the airport and real-time flight updates directly from the Flight Information Display System (FIDS).</p> <p>The app also allows users to find relevant and up-to-date information about</p>

<p>relevan dan terkini tentang penerbangan, bandara, dan destinasi wisata. Selain itu, aplikasi Travelin menawarkan keamanan yang pasti dan sistem pembayaran yang terjamin aman. Dengan demikian, aplikasi Travelin sangat berguna bagi pengguna karena memudahkan perjalanan udara dengan lebih mudah dan nyaman.</p> <p>Untuk mendapatkan aplikasi Travelin sangatlah mudah, cukup unduh aplikasi Travelin dari App Store atau Play Store, cari logo uniknya berwarna merah dengan huruf 't'. Lakukan pendaftaran dengan mudah yaitu mengisi data diri, lalu aplikasi siap digunakan. Tapi, jangan lupa untuk menggunakan lokasi bandara di tempat kamu berada saat itu.</p>	<p>flights, airports and tourist destinations. In addition, the Travelin app offers guaranteed security and a secured payment system. Thus, the Travelin app is very useful for users as it makes air travel easier and more convenient.</p> <p>To get the Travelin application is very easy, just download the Travelin application from the App Store or Play Store, and look for the unique red logo with the letter 't'. Register easily by filling in your personal data, then the application is ready to use. But, don't forget to use the airport location where you are at that time.</p>
<p>CONCLUSION</p>	
<p>Peluncuran resmi Travelin mengukir awal era baru dalam industri penerbangan. Tak sekadar aplikasi, Travelin menjadi sahabat setia dalam setiap perjalanan. Dari memesan tiket hingga menemukan tempat menginap terbaik, Travelin hadir untuk membuat pengalaman perjalananmu tak terlupakan.</p> <p>Kisah Travelin baru saja dimulai. Dengan fokus pada inovasi dan pengalaman pengguna yang tak terlupakan, PT Angkasa Pura II bertekad untuk terus mengembangkan layanan dan fitur. Jadi, bersiaplah memasuki dunia baru yang praktis dan seru bersama Travelin.</p>	<p>The official launch of Travelin marks the beginning of a new era in the airline industry. More than just an app, Travelin has become a loyal companion on every journey. From purchasing tickets to finding the best places to stay, Travelin is here to make your travel experience unforgettable.</p> <p>The Travelin story has just begun. With a focus on innovation and an unforgettable user experience, PT Angkasa Pura II is determined to continue developing services and features. So, get ready to enter a new world of convenience and excitement with Travelin.</p>
<p>CLOSING</p>	
<p>Sebagai pionir baru dalam dunia perjalanan di Indonesia, Travelin telah menjadi sumber inspirasi dan teman setia bagi setiap orang. Pada masa yang akan datang, aplikasi ini tidak hanya menjadi alat praktis, tetapi juga menjadi katalisator bagi pertumbuhan pariwisata, membuka pintu bagi lebih banyak orang untuk menemukan keajaiban yang tersembunyi di negeri ini.</p> <p>Kita berharap bahwa Travelin akan menjadi simbol perpaduan antara teknologi dan keindahan alam yang membawa dampak positif bagi masyarakat lokal dan lingkungan sekitarnya. Kita percaya bahwa dengan terus berinovasi dan mendengarkan suara</p>	<p>As a new pioneer in the world of travel in Indonesia, Travelin has become a source of inspiration and a loyal friend for everyone. In the future, the app will not only be a practical tool, but also a catalyst for tourism growth, opening the door for more people to discover the hidden wonders of this country.</p> <p>We hope that Travelin will become a symbol of the fusion between technology and natural beauty that brings positive impact to local communities and the surrounding environment. We believe that by continuously innovating and listening to the voices of users,</p>

pengguna, Travelin akan terus menjadi pemimpin dalam industri perjalanan di Indonesia.

Terima kasih telah setia menonton video ini. Mari kita sambut masa depan dengan senyum ceria dan semangat yang menyala-nyala. Mari kita terus berpetualang, menjelajahi setiap sudut negeri dengan Travelin di genggaman kita. Segera miliki Travelin di genggaman Anda dan ciptakan kisah-kisah baru yang tak terlupakan di bumi Indonesia

Travelin will continue to be a leader in the travel industry in Indonesia.

Thank you for watching this video. Let's welcome the future with a cheerful smile and a burning spirit. Let's keep travelling, exploring every corner of the country with Travelin in our hands. Have Travelin in your hand and create new unforgettable stories on Indonesian soil.

The use of the script in the video is in this link:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1VW6pDjm4ybvoJ3V3EL7EdUPyEQzph9-f/view?usp=drivesdk>

Some screen shots from the video are presented in the following table.

Table 2. Various Screen Shots of the Video

The novelty of this study lies in its specific focus on developing a video script for a particular mobile application, "Travelin," at PT. Angkasa Pura II Palembang, an airport. This contrasts with the previous studies, which primarily focus on broader tourism destinations. By focusing on a specific application, the study delves into the practical considerations of creating a video script that effectively guides users through a digital process, in this case, digital check-in. This provides valuable insights into crafting clear and concise instructions for technology-based services within a specific organizational context. Furthermore, the study emphasizes the importance of language clarity and conciseness within the context of a technological application. It highlights the need for simplified sentences, contemporary language, and the avoidance of redundancy, which are crucial for ensuring user comprehension and engagement. The study also provides specific language-related suggestions, such as refining diction, addressing Indonesian affixes (e.g., "di-"), italicizing English terms, and converting complex sentences to simpler structures. This level of detail in language-specific recommendations is a unique contribution, demonstrating a nuanced understanding of linguistic considerations within the context of a multilingual audience interacting with a digital platform.

DISCUSSION

The discussion was focused on the inappropriate parts as advised and suggested by the experts. There were some parts of the script that needed to be revised: hook, prologue, body and conclusion. First, the hook was commented not interesting enough if related to the objectives of designing a script for a descriptive video. The hook was a start to attract the audience's attention and could start with a fact, an anecdote, or even a quote. It serves as a captivating introduction to the video. It must also use interesting words to immediately grab the audience's attention and convey the purpose of the video using a fact about the efficiency of using the Travelin app with

interesting words (Friedman, 2014; Satoesa, 2020).

Second, the use of words in the prologue was not subtle enough, meaning that it needed better words for the diction to make it easier to convey information well. The prologue provides an overview of what will be discussed because it is an introduction to what will be explained in more depth later (Satoesa, 2020). It is preferable that this section uses words that can provide an introduction that makes viewers have a clear understanding (Muslimin, 2018).

Next, in the body section, the history of the Travelin application was contrary to the theory from Satoea (2020), because the body section should only explain important information about the application. The words used were also too stiff, it would be better to use words that were trendier and uptodate. There was a convoluted use of affixes and it was suggested for the body section, the explanation should be short, concise, and clear (Cockerham, 2016 and Friedman, 2014). The feature explanation was enough once, because the explanation of the feature was repeated in the last paragraph.

Finally, in the conclusion section there was no summary of the important points in the body. The conclusion is a section that summarises the main points that have been presented in the body (Cockerham, 2016; Friedman, 2014; Satoesa, 2020). There were no encouraged viewers to download or visit the website for more information as well. The encouragement to download the app in a more subtle way was in the last paragraph 'Jadi, bersiaplah memasuki dunia baru yang praktis dan seru bersama Travelin'.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, designing the Travelin application video script involved five steps. First, during the preliminary investigation, the writer researched video script writing by reading journals and gathering comprehensive information about the Travelin application from the official

website, blog articles, and user reviews. The second step was designing, where an outline for the script was developed. In the third step, realisation/construction, the writer drafted the script for the Travelin video. The fourth step involved testing, evaluation, and revision. The script was reviewed by a scriptwriting expert, an Indonesian language expert, and an English language expert. They provided feedback on simplifying sentences, using trendy language, avoiding repetition, and correctly using diction, the prefix "di-", and italicization for English words in Indonesian scripts. Finally, the implementation step involved all experts' feedback, and generated the script as the final version to be in the video. In essence, this study contributes novel insights into the creation of effective video scripts for specific technological applications, particularly within the context of airport services. By emphasizing the importance of clear communication, user-friendliness, and cultural sensitivity in the design of such instructional materials, this study provides valuable guidance for organizations seeking to improve user experience and enhance the effectiveness of their digital services.

For future study, it is recommended to expand the research and information-gathering process to gain a deeper understanding of the subject. Involving more experts from the beginning of the script design process is also advised, as their input can provide better guidance and enhance the script's quality. Additionally, it is suggested to use experienced videographers and high-quality cameras to produce videos with better overall quality.

REFERENCES

- Andini, M. P. (2024). Video Copywriting of Pempek Cek Yeti. *Holistics Journal: Hospitality and Linguistics*, 16(1), 26-38. <https://jurnal.polsri.ac.id/index.php/holistic/article/view/8845>
- Astuti, N.F. (2020). *3 Macam desain, lengkap dari fungsi hingga unsur unurnya*, merdeka.com. Retrieved from <https://www.merdeka.com/jabar/3-macamdesain-lengkap-dari-fungsi-hingga-unsurunurnya-klm.html> on 15 March 2024.
- Ayton, D. (2023). *Qualitative Research – a practical guide for health and social care researchers and practitioners*. Open Educational Resources Collective. Retrieved from <https://oercollective.caul.edu.au/qualitative-research/front-matter/introduction/> on 28

March 2024

- Birt, L., Scott, S., Cavers, D., Campbell, C., and Walter, F. (2016). Member Checking: A Tool to Enhance Trustworthiness or Merely a Nod to Validation? *Qualitative health research*, 26(13), 1802–1811. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732316654870>
- Cockerham, L. (2016). *7 Simple steps to writing an effective corporate video script*, Venture. Retrieved from <https://www.venturevideos.com/insights/how-to-write-a-corporate-video-script> on 14 March 2024.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach* (4th Ed.). Sage Publication, Inc.
- Fadli, M. R. (2021). Understanding the design of qualitative research methods. *Journal of Humanika*, 21(1), 33-34.
- Fadlurrahman, F. (2023). Writing a script for a short video promotion of Dapoer Cinta as a culinary destination in Palembang. *Holistics Journal: Hospitality and Linguistics*, 15(2), 31-44. <https://jurnal.polsri.ac.id/index.php/holistic/article/view/9203>
- Friedmann, A. (2014). *Writing for Visual Media (4th Edition)*. New York: Focal.
- Gustiani, S. (2019). Research and Development (R&D) Method as A Model Design in Educational Research and Its Alternatives. *Journal of Holistics*, 11(2).
- Herring, P. (2016). *Complete English Grammar Rules*. Colorado, Canada: CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform.
- La, J., Bil, C. and Heiets, I. (2020). Impact of digital technologies on airline operations, *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, 56(C), 63–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2021.09.008>.
- Liu, M., and Huang, W. (2016). The effectiveness of video in socialization: An examination of visual and auditory elements. *Journal of Communication*, 67(3), 432–451. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcom.12228>.
- Magaldi, D., and Berler, M. (2020). Semi-structured interviews. In V. Zeigler-Hill & T. K. Shackelford (Eds.), *Encyclopedia of Personality and Individual Differences*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-24612-3857>
- Ministry of Education and Culture. (2022). *EYD 5th edition*. Retrieved from <https://ejaan.kemdikbud.go.id/eyd/> on 6 April 2024.
- Muslimin, N. (2018). *Bikin filmyuk!*. Yogyakarta: Araska.
- Nadjmuddin, M. (2019). Writing the Script of Native Advertising Video for Tanjung and Blongsong Clothes. *Journal of Holistics*, 11 (2), 2085-4021.
- Patton, M. Q. (2015). Evaluation in the field: The need for site visit standards. *American Journal of Evaluation*, 36(4), 444-460.
- Plomp, T. (1997). *Development Research on/in educational development*. Netherlands: Twente University Press.
- Satoeasa. (2020). *Youtube video script making*. Youtube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jrQq0QhfgkI&t=575s>.
- Thabroni, G. (2019). *Pengertian desain (lengkap) berdasarkan pendapat para ahli*, Serupa.id. Retrieved from <https://serupa.id/pengertian-desain/> on 14 March 2024.
- Tristiawati. (2014). *Script / naskah dan rancangan isi program media pembelajaran*. Academia.edu. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/7365604/SCRIPT_NASKAH_DAN_RANCANGAN_ISI_PROGRAM_MEDIA_PEMBELAJARAN?auto=download.
- Viranda, S. H. (2024). Designing a video script of New Ocarina as one of tourism destination in Batam. *Holistics Journal: Hospitality and Linguistics*, 16(1), 39-53. <https://jurnal.polsri.ac.id/index.php/holistic/article/view/8834>

- Walidin, W., Saifullah, and Tabrani. (2015). *Metodologi penelitian kualitatif & grounded theory*. FTK Ar-Raniry Press.
- Yandi, M. A. P., Shahab, A., & Sari, E. A. (2023). Writing video script of Green Canyon to promote tourism destination in Lahat. *Holistics Journal: Hospitality and Linguistics*, 15(1), 30-44. <https://jurnal.polsri.ac.id/index.php/holistic/article/view/8235>
- Yanwardhana, E. (2022). *Harga tiket pesawat meroket gila-gilaan, begini penjelasannya*, CNBC Indonesia. Retrieved from <https://www.cnbcindonesia.com/news/20220718160143-4-356488/harga-tiket-pesawat-meroket-gila-gilaan-begini-penjasannya> on 5 March 2024.